

EXPLORING THE ESSENTIAL FEATURES OF THOMAS HARDY'S NOVEL "TESS OF THE D'URBERVILLES"

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Annotation. This article analyzes the life and work of English novelist Thomas Hardy and his most famous novel , "Tess of the D'Urbervilles". It examines the historical background of the novel's creation , its main ideas and themes , the characterization of Tess and the author's critique and social and moral conventions. The study aims to reveal the philosophical and humanistic meaning of the novel and to highlight Hardy's compassionate view of women's fate in a partriarchal society.

Key words. English realism, social injustice, moral hypocrisy, female oppression, fate versus freedom, moral double standards, social conventions, inner purity, conscience and morality, nature symbolism, feminist thought, individual versus society.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется жизнь и творчество английского писателя Томаса Харди и его самый известный роман «Тесс из рода Д'Эрбервилей». Рассматривается исторический контекст создания романа, его основные идеи и темы, характеристика Тесс, критика автора и социально-моральные нормы. Цель исследования — раскрыть философский и гуманистический смысл романа и подчеркнуть сострадательный взгляд Харди на судьбу женщин в патриархальном обществе.

Ключевые слова. Английский реализм, социальная несправедливость, моральное лицемерие, угнетение женщин, судьба против свободы, двойные моральные стандарты, социальные условности, внутренняя чистота, совесть и мораль, символика природы, феминистская мысль, индивид против общества.

Introduction

The second half of the 19th century in English literature was a period when social issues , human destiny and moral values were widely explored. Thomas Hardy (1840-1928) one of the most outstanding representative of English realism , portrayed in his works the conflict between man and society , fate and freedom and the tragic condition of women . In his novel, Hardy often emphasized that "society oppresses the individual". His stories reveal the moral hypocrisy and rigid

conventions of Victorian England . His (1891) novel “Tess of the D’Urbervilles “ became one of the most controversial yet influential works of English literature.

Main part

Thomas Hardy was born in 1890 in the small village of Stinsford , Dorset ,England into a poor but educated family. He began his career as an architect but later turned to literature , inspired by his love for nature and human physiology. His early novels –Under the Greenwood Tree (1872) , Far from the Madding Crowd (1874), and The Mayor of Casterbridge (1886)- established him as a major realist novelist . However , it was “ Tess of the D’Urbervilles “ that made him a world –famous author. Hardy was frequently criticized by the conservative public for challenging moral and religious conventions . Yet he remained devoted to his artistic mission – to expose injustice and to portray the emotional and spiritual struggle of ordinary people especially women. Hardy complete “Tess of the D’Urbervilles” in 1891 , because of its daring themes – female purity , sexual exploitation , and social hypocrisy- several magazines refused to publish it. The novel was first printed in a censored form in 1890, but the full version published in 1891 caused both scandal and admiration. Today, it is recognized as one of the greatest works of English realism and early feminist thought.

The novel tells the story of Tess Durbeyfield, a poor country girl whose life is destroyed by social injustice. Hoping to improve her family’s fortune , Tess visits the wealthy D’Urbervilles where she meets Alec D’Urbervilles who deceives and violates her . Thought innocent , Tess becomes an outcast in the eyes of society. Later she falls in love with Angel Clare , a kind young man . However , after learning about Tess’s past Angel rejects her – unable to forgive what society calls “sin”. Eventually, Tess kills Alec in despair and is executed for murder. Though this tragic story, Hardy exposes the cruelty of moral double standards and the suffering caused by rigid Victorian values. The novel’s central idea is that true purity lies not in social reputation , but in moral integrity and compassion.

Tess is one of the most complex and emotionally rich heroines in English literature. She is innocent , sensitive , loyal and deeply connected with nature . Although she is victimized by society , she preserves her inner purity. Tess represent Hardy’s ideal of a natural , moral and spiritual woman who remains true to herself despite external judgment. Through Tess, Hardy proclaims that “it is not society, but conscience, that defines a person’s worth” Hardy’s novel vividly portrays the injustice faced by women in 19th-century England . The double standards of morality condemn women like Tess while excusing men like Alec .

Hardy's criticism is clear: society punishes women for what it tolerates in men . This moral imbalance makes Tess's tragedy not just personal , but universal – the tragedy of all women silenced by social norms.

Nature plays a vital symbolic role in the novel. Hardy uses landscapes and weather to mirror Tess's emotions.

- Spring symbolizes hope and renewal.
- Winter and night represent suffering and despair.
- The field and flower reflect Tess's innocence and harmony with nature.

Hardy portrays nature as both Tess's companion and witness – it is a living force that feels her pain and mirror her destiny.

The relationship between Tess and Angel is central to the novel's emotional depth. Angel's love is sincere but limited by moral pride . When Tess confesses her past , he abandons her – showing the hypocrisy of men who preach forgiveness but fail to practice it. Only later does Angel realize his mistake , but by then Tess's fate is sealed. Their reunion is brief yet deeply symbolic – a moment of spiritual peace before the inevitable tragedy.

Hardy's style blends realism with symbolism and lyrical description. His language is poetic and filled with biblical and philosophical references. He often combines simple rural dialogue with profound reflections on fate and morality. This unique mixture of realism , naturalism and moral philosophy makes “ Tess of the D'Urbervilles “ not only a social novel but also a work of deep psychological and ethical meaning. When it was first published , the novel challenged the moral foundations of Victorian England . It forced readers to confront uncomfortable truths about gender , class, and justice. Today, “Tess of the D'Urbervilles” remains relevant as a timeless study of womanhood, morality, and human suffering . It is both a tragedy and a protest – a call for empathy and moral fairness.

In Conclusion

Through “ Tess of the D'Urbervilles”, Thomas Hardy reveals the cruelty of social judgment and the strength of a woman's soul . Tess's story shows that moral purity is an inner quality not a social label. Hardy's message is clear: “it is not society , but conscience , that judges us”. Tess's tragic fate continues to move readers reminding us of the eternal struggle between innocence and injustice.

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